

Title

Comparative effectiveness of biologic monotherapy for generalized pustular psoriasis:
protocol for a systematic review with narrative synthesis.

1. Background and Rationale

Generalized pustular psoriasis (GPP) is a rare, severe inflammatory skin disorder characterized by widespread sterile pustules and systemic inflammation. Although biologic have emerged as key treatment option, the comparative effectiveness of different agents remains uncertain due to the limited number of comparative studies—many of which have heterogeneous study designs and outcome measures. Recent clinical trials and observational studies have evaluated biologics that target immunomodulatory pathways such as interleukin (IL)-36 and IL-17. However, the rarity of GPP has resulted in small sample sizes, heterogeneous methodologies, and inconsistent outcome reporting—all of which could deter appropriate quantitative syntheses by limiting the feasibility of robust meta-analyses studies.

The proposed study will systematically review and narratively synthesize the available comparative evidence on biologic monotherapy for GPP, with exploratory quantitative comparisons where appropriate.

2. Objectives

To systematically identify, appraise, and synthesize evidence on the comparative effectiveness of biologic monotherapy for generalized pustular psoriasis.

3. Methods

3.1 Study Design

The proposed study will be a systematic review with narrative synthesis—and the conduct thereof would adhere to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.

3.2 Eligibility Criteria

Population

Studies involving patients diagnosed with generalized pustular psoriasis (GPP), regardless of age, sex, or geographic location, will be included.

Interventions

Biologic monotherapy targeting inflammatory pathways relevant to GPP (e.g., IL-36 inhibitors, IL-17 inhibitors, etc).

Comparators

- Monotherapy with other biologic agents
- Placebo or vehicle

Outcomes

Studies must report at least one validated GPP outcome measure, including:

- Generalized Pustular Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (GPPASI)
- Generalized Pustular Psoriasis Physician Global Assessment (GPPGA)

Study Designs

Eligible designs will include:

- Randomized controlled trials
- Non-randomized comparative studies (e.g., cohort studies, subgroup analyses, post-hoc analyses)

Excluded:

- Single-arm studies
- Case reports and case series
- Reviews and editorials

Language

Only studies published in English will be included.

3.3 Information Sources

A systematic search will be conducted in the following databases:

- PubMed/MEDLINE
- ClinicalTrials.gov

Additional sources may be identified through reference mining.

3.4 Search Strategy

The search strategy will be designed to maximize sensitivity given the rarity of GPP.

Keywords and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) will include combinations of:

- “generalized pustular psoriasis”
- “biologic” OR “biological therapy”
- “trial” OR “effect” OR “efficacy” OR “comparative”

Search strategies will be adapted for each database.

3.5 Study Selection

Titles and abstracts will be screened independently by two reviewers. Full-text articles will then be assessed for eligibility. Discrepancies will be resolved through discussion with a third reviewer.

3.6 Data Extraction

Data will be extracted independently by two reviewers using a standardized form.

Extracted variables will include:

- Study characteristics (author, year, design)
- Participant characteristics (sample size, age, sex)
- Intervention details (drug, dose, route)
- Comparator(s)
- Outcome measures (GPPASI, GPPGA)
- Follow-up duration
- Key findings

3.7 Risk of Bias Assessment

The risk of bias of included studies will be assessed using appropriate tools from the Cochrane Collaboration:

- Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies – of Interventions (ROBINS-I) for non-randomized studies.

- Risk of Bias (RoB) for randomized trials.

Assessments will be conducted at the domain level rather than assigning an overall study score.

3.8 Data Synthesis

Given anticipated heterogeneity in study design, population, and outcome reporting, findings will be synthesized narratively. The synthesis will compare outcomes across biologic classes. Furthermore, clinical and methodological heterogeneity will be assessed qualitatively based on:

- Study design
- Patient characteristics
- Intervention type and dosing
- Outcome definitions

3.9 Exploratory Quantitative Analysis

Where feasible, exploratory quantitative comparisons will be conducted to summarize trends across studies. These analyses may include: descriptive comparison of proportions achieving clinical improvement, summary measures of relative differences between interventions. These analyses could be hypothesis-generating.

4. Ethics and Dissemination

Ethical approval will not be required, as this study will solely be based on data from previously published studies.